

Detector Resource Names (previously Geographical names) for NSW underground data sources and data destinations

Version 0.10, 14 March 2022¹

Proposed here is a geographical or logical naming scheme for NSW data sources and data destinations. In this document, the data sources and data destinations are called “Detector Resource Names”. Detector Resources, such as sROC’s on FEB’s, SCA’s on FEB’s and other boards, map to E-links. Detector Resource Names allow subscribing to E-links by names that reflect their functional position in the NSW detector. This is done by using a “FELIX Resource Identifier” (FID) and the two databases, as described in:

<https://espace.cern.ch/ATLAS-NSW-ELX/Shared%20Documents/DAQ/LinkMappingSpecification.pdf>

1. A mapping between Detector Resource Names to the fibre bundle (an MTP-24) from underground identified by a visible label, the fibre number in the bundle and the E-link on that fibre. This is the “FELIX Resource Identifier” (FELIX-ID or FID). The detector group populates and maintains this database. See the Appendix for the format of the E-link identification (the Connector Id and Transport Id in the above referenced document.)
2. A mapping between the FID, i.e. an MTP-24 fibre bundle, and a particular FELIX server, FELIX FPGA board and the optical connector on the FPGA board to which the fibre bundle is connected. TDAQ populates and maintains this database.

Detector Resource names are a string of location and attribute values, separated by "/"s. For example:

MM-A/V0/L1A/strip/S4/L3/R11/E3

refers to L1A data from Micromegas, Version 0, Endcap A, strips, Sector 4, Layer 3, Radial position 11, sROC 3.

All the numbers start from 0, preserving coherency with numerical representation. In other words, sector numbers, for instance, are in the interval 0-15, corresponding to sectors 1-16 in the usual ATLAS "Enumeration by the human eye". So, sector 4 in the example corresponds to sector 5 in that enumeration.

The Detector Resource Name begins with the ATLAS Detector ID that corresponds to the DetectorID’s listed in “The raw event format in the ATLAS Trigger & DAQ”, <https://edms.cern.ch/document/445840/5.0.4>, followed by a string defined by the detector.

There are no wild characters, since that would imply resolving to a list of resources.

Each Detector Resource also has a binary representation, the Detector Resource ID. The high byte is as defined in the above document. Detectors are free to construct the low 24 bits as they like.

For NSW, the names of the possible locations and attributes are shown in the table below. To the right of each are shown its possible values. See the Appendix for details of the attributes.

¹ The version number of the present document has been changed (0.8 instead of 8) to reflect the format version number in the ID. The major version number corresponds to the ID version number. That is 0, since the proposed format will be used at P1 for the first time, after the present document version has been modified last time.

# bits	attribute	abbrev	Possible values						
8	DetectorID		MM-A: 0x6b	MM-C: 0x6c	sTGC-A: 0x6d	sTGC-C: 0x6e			
3	version	V	0x0						
1	reserved								
3	data-type		L1A: 0	Monitor: 1	to-SCA: 2	from-SCA: 3	TTC: 4	L1Ainfo: 5	Ext: 6 Exc: 7
3	resource-type	T	Pad FEB: 0	Strip FEB: 1	Trig Proc: 2	Pad Trig: 3	L1DDC: 4	ADDC: 5	Router: 6 Rim-L1DDC: 7
4	sector	S	0..15						
3	layer	L	0..7						
4	radius	R	sTGC: 0..2	MM: 0..15	Rim-L1DDC: A/P		MM L1DDC: E/O	sTGC L1DDC: P/S	
3	E-link	E	sROC: 0..3	Rim-L1DDC SCA: 0/1 (prim/aux)					

32

- A version field has been included to allow for format evolution whenever needed.
- For bidir links, like SCA, the data-type includes an indication of the direction.
- Monitor data-type refers to non-L1A data sent to FELIX.
- In the string representation, for readability, resources with only numeric values are preceded by a one-letter abbreviation of the location or attribute, for example:
MM-A/V0/L1A/strip/S4/L3/R11/E3
- The values for each location/attribute used for the binary representation, where each is a fixed bit field in the 32-bit Detector Resource ID, are shown in the table.
- The binary representation of the above example would be (4 bits, 3 for version number and 1 reserved, are included in parentheses):
0x6b | (0 | 0 |) 0 | 1 | 1 | 4 | 3 | 11 | 3 | = 0x6b (000 0) 000 001 0100 011 1011 011 = 0x6b00'51DB

Numeric values for sector, layer, radius and channel group follow the NSW convention for locations internal to computer codes, i.e. beginning with zero. See the NSW TDR, Appendix A.2, "Naming Conventions" (<https://cds.cern.ch/record/1552862>). Starting from 1 ("Enumerations for the human eye") would require an extra bit for each of these fields.

Multiple L1A data E-links from a single Front end board

For front-end boards, specific VMM's cannot be given a detector resource name because the mapping of the VMM's to the ROC output E-links is not static, but is configurable in the ROC. Subscriptions will be done to ROC E-link ports, called sROC's: the data will identify from which VMM it came. It may be that we subscribe to all four ports and are told which ones are not enabled, i.e. are not connected to any VMM's.

The VMM number is coded into data and associated to each hit. Reconstruction and monitoring software can associate VMM's to each hit independently of the specific E-link used to read it out from a FEB. On the other hand, using sROC number uniquely identifies the E-link used to transport data.

For configuration and monitoring, subscription to each VMM is not needed, since they are configured and monitored through OPC/SCA, with each VMM addressed by a specific SCA SPI chip enable.

E-links uniquely identified without the E field, can be absent in the Detector Identifier. That shall correspond to a value 0 in the corresponding numeric ID field.

Unexpected TTC fan-out on the MM-L1DDC

More than one MM FE board can have their TTC input E-link and BC clock sourced by the same physical outputs from the GBTx on the MM-L1DDC. Consequently their Detector Resource Name will be the same. The pairs that share a single source are: (FEB9, FEB11), (FEB10, FEB12), (FEB13, FEB15), (FEB14, FEB16).

OPC-UA path

The Detector Resource Name string should be used to identify OPC-UA SCA endpoints in the OPC-UA SCA xml configuration file, i.e. the value of the **opcNodeID** field. In preparation of the configuration file, the Detector Resource Name will be translated to an FID and stored in the xml configuration file. This means that the value of the **opcServerIp** field is not hard-coded in the file, but rather the OPC-UA client should use the FID to look-up the OPC server's IP address and connect to the standard OPC server port.

Appendix: Format of the LinkID (LID) and Transport ID (TID) fields in the FELIXID (FID)

The format of the 64-bit FELIX-Id (FID) for NSW is:

	63..60	59..52	51..36		35..22		21..8			7..0
Field	Version	DetectorID	ConnectorID		LinkID		TransportID			StreamID
Width	4	8	16		14		14			8
Sub-field			Trunk-ID (1.8)	MTP24 ID (1..12)	V	LinkID	E-link	Dir	Protocol	
Sub-width			8	8	1	13	6	1	7	

The TrunkID and MTP24-ID fields of the ConnectorID are specific to NSW.

The E-link field is the low bit of the E-link in the 80-bit GBT word, divided by 2. $EC=112/2=56$, $IC=114/2=57$. It corresponds to the -I option of the **fupload** and **felink** commands, except for the factor 2. The reasoning behind this is that using an E-link definition that includes the E-link width to define a connection path is not good because the same GBTx E-link input pin may be configurable for different speeds/widths. The speed/width and other attributes of the E-link are defined by **elinkconfig** and should not be defined in both places.

For example the E-link whose data starts at bit 0, -I 0, can be configured as a 2, 4 or 8-bit e-link without changing any physical connections.

V=1 for virtual E-links; Dir=1 for To-FrontEnd links; Protocol=0 for GBTx links; StreamID=0.

Appendix: Details of the attributes

Each E-link has all the attributes in the table, from detectorID, version thru' "chan-group". The choice of values for each attribute depends on the data-type and resource type.

- "version": this attribute says which version of the Detector Resource Names definition is used. The document defines Version 0.
- "data-type":
 - L1A data: obvious
 - Monitor: some resource types (Trigger Proc, Router) have E-links for sending out monitoring data (not SCA monitoring)
 - To-SCA, From-SCA: for FEBs, they have the same E-group/E-link value, even though there are two physical links, one in each direction. They are different fibres in the MTP-24. For Rim-L1DDCs the values are different.
 - TTC: Means this E-link needs to be configured as a TTC E-link. (It is From-FELIX)
 - Pad Trigger: has SCA, Monitor, L1A and TTC E-links
 - Router: has SCA, Monitor, AUX and TTC E-links
 - L1A-info: not applicable to our fibres
 - Ext (data type 6) means "Extra Data" and replaces "Aux" in previous versions to avoid confusion between Auxiliary Data and Auxiliary Rim-L1DDC.

- Exc (data type 7) identifies exception messages from the Trigger Processor. These messages allow software to generate error messages to the error message system, or to increment counters in the Information System.
- "resource-type": These are the kinds of devices we have that are connected to fibres. Note that "strip FEB" can mean either an sTGC sFEB or an MMFE8, depending on the value of DetectorID.
- Sector, layer: obvious, but be careful how layers are defined. We want 0 to N-1, with increasing Z.
- "radius": This is the radial position of the FEB or ADDC. 0 to N-1 in increasing radius. Note that for MMFE8, half the FEBs (with even radius) in a layer are connected to one L1DDC, half (with odd radius) to another L1DDC. In case boards are unique on left or right side, the R field, previously defined as L or R (without numeric value), identifying the lowering or rising phi position on the sector, is defined, to allow unique interpretation in case of cabling errors, as:
 - E (even) and O (odd) for micromegas. The corresponding numeric id field shall be 0 for even and 1 for odd;
 - P (pFEB) and S (sFEB) for sTGC. The corresponding numeric field shall be 0 for pFEB and 1 for sFEB.
 - A (Auxiliary) and P (Primary) for Rim-L1DDC. (Both are on a single PCB.) The corresponding numeric field shall be 0 for Auxiliary and 1 for Primary.
- "E-link": for FEBs, this is the sROC id. For ADDCs, it is the ART ASIC number on the board. Which ART is ART0 needs to be defined. SCA's in the Rim-L1DDC have two E-links. No E field shall be defined for other boards (numeric field shall be 0).

History

Version	Name	Change
V5	L Levinson	Changed to-FELIX direction to be value 1 in TID Added note on TTC being many-to-one for some MM TTC E-links
V6	E Pasqualucci	Definition of R field for radius-independent boards. No E-field when e-links are uniquely identified by the rest of the ID.
V7	L Levinson	Edited to reflect the final specification of the ConnectorID and TransportID fields of the FELIX-ID. Also describe the intention to store the FID translated from the Detector Resource Name in the OPC UA xml configuration file.
V 0.8	E. Pasqualucci	Change document version format to reflect ID format number. L and R in R field changed to E and O for micromega and P and S for sTGC.
V 0.9	E. Pasqualucci	As for previous version, introduced P for primary Rim and A for Auxiliary Rim
V 0.10	E. Pasqualucci, L. Levinson	Data type 6 renamed "Extra Data" to avoid confusion between "Auxiliary Data" and "Auxiliary RIM"